

UTILISING MICROWAVE GENERATED METALLIC Fe⁰ TO IMPROVE LOW POWER WATER EXTRACTION FROM ICE RICH LUNAR REGOLITH ANALOGUES. A. Bhutta¹, J.D. Cole¹, J. Bowen², M. Anand¹, and S. Lim³

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Introduction:

Microwave heating of lunar regolith is considered a promising application for in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) on the Moon, both for construction and volatile extraction. This is because it provides volumetric heating in low-conductivity regolith, avoids moving parts, and can, in principle, be implemented with low electrical power. Laboratory work has shown that Fe-rich lunar mare simulants such as JSC-1A couple strongly to 2.45 GHz microwaves, undergoing rapid sintering, melting and thermal runaway at powers of 0.25–1.00 kW [1], and that low-power (0.25 kW) microwave heating can extract ~65–95 % of water from icy simulants over tens of minutes [2]. However, nearly all such studies face a major shortcoming: they neglect the combined effects of space weathering on the dielectric response of the actual lunar regolith.

A key product of space weathering of lunar regolith is nanophase metallic iron (np-Fe⁰), which is believed to form via reduction and vapour-deposition processes in agglutinitic glass and amorphous grain rims. These np-Fe⁰ grains are known to dominate optical reddening, darkening and magnetic susceptibility, and are widely used as maturity indicators in both returned samples and orbital datasets. Yet their role in microwave coupling, dielectric loss and volatile release behaviour remains poorly constrained. Taylor and Meek [3] hypothesised that the remarkable microwave response of mature Apollo mare soils, compared with np-Fe⁰-free simulants, is largely controlled by np-Fe⁰ and Fe-rich phases acting as highly absorbing areas [3], but this has never been quantified for icy regolith analogues relevant to lunar polar volatiles.

We will use microwave heating of ilmenite in a SiC crucible to produce a glassy, Fe⁰-bearing analogue of agglutinatic lunar soil, with sub-micron metallic iron inclusions. This will allow us to investigate how space-weathering-style metallic Fe in the regolith matrix influences low-power microwave water extraction efficiency from hydrated lunar analogues, and to assess whether maturity-related metrics (including Fe⁰ content and associated spectral changes) can serve as predictive indicators of extraction performance. Although our microwave-produced Fe⁰ grains are predicted to be in the size range of 100 to 500 nm, which are coarser than

the ultra-small np-Fe⁰ (few to tens of nm) responsible for lunar spectral reddening, they overlap in the size range of Fe⁰ globules reported in agglutinatic glass and can therefore provide a practical analogue for the Fe⁰-rich component of mature soils. [4]

Methods: This project aims to investigate how space-weathering maturity, mimicked by microwave-induced reduction of Fe-bearing phases (e.g., ilmenite) to metallic Fe, modifies microwave coupling and water-extraction performance in icy regolith analogues. In parallel with microwave experiments that mix manufactured nanoparticles into regolith analogues, we will also focus on metallic iron generated in situ by microwave processing, which more closely resembles the reduction expected in the actual regolith.

The latter experimental programme has four components:

1. *Microwave synthesis of metallic iron-enhanced ilmenite.*

Natural ilmenite powder is placed in a silicon carbide crucible, and then microwave energy is applied in a single-mode cavity at 2.45 GHz using a heating protocol previously used by Tang et al. [4]. The aim is to induce partial melting and reduction of ilmenite and other Fe-oxides to metallic Fe, without changing the bulk composition. Earlier work has shown that ilmenite exhibits high dielectric loss, couples efficiently with microwaves, and can be reduced to metallic iron at $\geq \sim 1300$ °C; added Fe⁰ generates densified, sintered products and enhances coupling [4].

2. *Microstructural characterisation.*

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) will be employed to characterise microstructural changes in the ilmenite powder before and after microwave-induced weathering, with a particular focus on the in-situ generation of metallic Fe. We will identify major mineral phases (e.g., ilmenite, olivine, pyroxene, plagioclase, glass) and assess the distribution and morphology of newly formed Fe particles. This microstructural evidence will be crucial for understanding how these ‘space-weathered’ products relate to dielectric loss

mechanisms and how they might influence the thermal evolution and volatile transport paths during water extraction, thus providing a qualitative basis for the observed quantitative changes in dielectric properties.

3. *Preparation of lunar-regolith analogues.*

The cooled ilmenite glass product will then be blended with the low-Ti mare simulant JSC-1A at predetermined weight fractions. This mixture yields a regolith analogue that simultaneously contains glass-rich agglutinates with embedded metallic iron and the mineralogy of mature lunar soil.

4. *Microwave water extraction from icy regolith analogues previously microwaved.*

Building on previous 0.25 kW experiments performed with JSC-1A, LHS-1 and LMS-1 icy simulants, we will prepare granular icy regolith analogues (3–15 wt % H₂O) [2], initially using the “mud-pie” method using both pristine and pre-weathered analogues. These samples will be heated at 2.45 GHz under vacuum at fixed low input powers (\approx 0.25–0.40 kW), using a Dynamic Mass Instrument to monitor real-time mass loss. Key observables include: (i) temperature–time histories, (ii) sublimation-front changes and crust formation inferred from post-heating expectations, and (iii) extraction ratio (grams H₂O per Wh) as a function of Fe⁰ content and ilmenite abundance.

coupling, and promoting thermal runaway to enhance volatile (water-ice) extraction.

Recent laboratory work on np-Fe⁰-doped CLRS-2 simulant suggests that \sim 1 wt % np-Fe⁰ is sufficient to increase densification using microwave sintering [6], while other studies of microwave extraction highlight how subtle changes in thermal properties and gas vapour flow can strongly affect water yields.

Ultimately, this project aims to determine whether maturity-sensitive observables, such as spectral reddening, can serve as predictors of microwave extraction performance. If successful, this would provide a bridge between orbital and landed remote-sensing datasets and the design and site-selection of low-power microwave ISRU systems, including concepts such as the Microwave Heating Demonstrator (MHD) payload currently under study.

References:

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Figure 1 Microwave Heating Unit (MHU) at the Open University. [5]

By systematically comparing unweathered and microwave-weathered materials across a range of Fe/ilmenite concentrations and hydration levels, we will test the hypothesis that metallic Fe⁰ formed in situ acts as an internal microwave susceptor, lowering the power threshold for efficient electromagnetic